

AI-Enabled Decision Support for Human Decision-Making and Operational Performance: A Systematic Review

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Abstract – Recent advances in Artificial Intelligence have seen increasing adoption in organizations, especially in business operations to support complex decision-making processes. While prior research mainly focuses on AI automation decision-making, less attention is paid to AI decision support on human, especially in business operations contexts. This study presents a systematic literature review on how AI-enabled decision support influences human operational decision-making and improves operational performance in business operations. This systematic literature review is conducted through the PRISMA-based review protocol, and relevant studies are identified from Scopus and IEEE Xplore databases, which were later screened based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. This resulted in 15 selected studies, which were then analyzed to identify publication year, research method, author countries, decision-making task, operational context, and effect on human operational decision-making and operational performance outcomes. The findings of the reviewed studies indicate that AI-enabled decision support influence decision-making efficiency, adaptability, situational awareness, explainability, and confidence, while operational performance impact indicate there is an improvement primarily on process efficiency, productivity, risk management, resource-related efficiency, resilience and sustainability. This findings provide

insights for businesses seeking to implement AI decision support systems rather than replacing it. This study contributes by providing a synthesis of empirical evidence on AI-enabled decision support systems, highlighting the influence on human operational decision-making and organizational operational performance.

Keywords – AI-Enabled Decision Support, Operational Performance, Business Operations, Human-AI Collaboration, Systematic Literature Review

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, artificial intelligence (AI) has become a hot topic as it advanced rapidly, resulting in increasing adoption among organizations and businesses. Businesses begin to utilize artificial intelligence as it becomes an integral part of business, especially in the applications of operation management (OM) elements such as manufacturing, product development, services, and supply chain [1] for enabling businesses to overcome traditional operational inefficiencies [2]. AI is being embedded in organizations decision-making, not through human replacement but as a complement in handling ambiguous and equivocal situations [3].

AI-based decision support systems have emerged in revolutionizing decision-making process across industrial domains [4] particularly machine learning based decision support systems, which are designed to support production planning and control through predicting operational problems and suggesting recommendations [5]. Recent developments indicate that businesses are increasingly exploring AI automated decision-making within organizational decision-making. This leads to concerns regarding the tradeoff of accuracy, as AI is more accurate, but legitimacy and accountability matter, which prompted regulatory discussions and emphasized human oversight in AI decision-making [6].

Artificial intelligence (AI) has increasingly been applied in business operations to enhance operational capabilities and performance. Prior studies report that AI improves visibility, efficiency, and operational processes, while encountering some challenges in the implementation. For instance, Helo and Hao's exploratory case study discusses how companies implement AI-enabled solutions within their existing business model to create business value in supply chain management [7], while Cannas et al.'s research examines the benefits and barriers of AI technologies in operations and supply chain management through a case study [8].

While integration of AI in business operations enhances operational capabilities and performance, it does not eliminate the need for effective operational decision-making. Recent studies show that AI is being applied to support operational decision-making tasks such as routing, forecasting, scheduling, and planning. For example, Sultana et al. propose an AI technique, such as a reinforcement learning approach, to enable real-time route formation in vehicle routing problems [9]. Similar studies integrate machine learning techniques to support production scheduling and planning in manufacturing industries, which reported an improvement in scheduling efficiency and operational performance [10].

Even though many studies about AI decision making are focused on AI automation, there are growing number of researchers doing AI

decision support systems that emphasize humans for operational decision making. AI decision support systems can help business operations and service operations provide recommendations and predictions. For instance, Koukaras et al. research study illustrates how AI-enabled decision support systems can be applied to support service operations in educational institutions to help administrators in forecasting, detecting irregular activities, and scheduling resources [11]. On the other hand, Sauer et al. research study develop decision support system integrated with machine learning to help production controllers predict missing parts at the assembly start and provide insights into part shortages in the manufacturing industry [5]. Another study proposes a decision support system integrated with computational intelligence and machine learning to monitor the injection molding process in real time, thus supporting operators in taking decision making process [12].

Currently, prior studies on AI-enabled decision support effects on human decision making evidence remain fragmented. For example, Laxar et al. research study experiment compared two kinds of AI-enabled clinical decision support systems (CDSS), one providing reasoning and the other without reasoning, to support physician helping critical ill patients, which results show no significant different on weight advice, and overall trust remains low [13]. On the other hand, Lowhagen et al. evaluates AI-based troubleshooting assistant to support workers, which results in improvement in human decision quality and supports less experienced decision makers [14]. These 2 findings indicate that effects on human decision making remain inconsistent depends on the context. As for operational performance improvement, existing evidence is fragmented across different business operations contexts.

Despite growing studies on AI-enabled decision support systems, most existing research emphasizes algorithmic performance and automation rather than AI decision support by humans. Moreover, empirical evidence on AI-enabled decision support effects on human decision making and its operational performance outcome remains limited and dispersed. To address this gap, this study

conducts a systematic literature review on AI-enabled decision support systems used by human decision-makers in business operations. The following research question guides the review:

RQ: How does AI-enabled decision support influence human operational decision-making and improve operational performance in business operations?

II. RESEARCH METHODS

The following research methods are structured into five sections: (A) information sources and search strategy, (B) Eligibility Criteria, (C) Selection Process, (D) Data Extraction, and (E) Data Analysis. The systematic literature review of the following study followed the PRISMA 2020 guidelines [15].

A. Information Sources and Search Strategy

The research was conducted on SCOPUS and IEEE Xplore databases in December 2025. Scopus was selected as it covers broad multidisciplinary coverage across business, management, and also provide high quality journals and conference proceedings. On the other hand, IEEE Xplore focuses more on technical and engineering-oriented research, which includes artificial intelligence, machine learning, and decision support systems. Both together provide coverage of the research on artificial intelligence, decision support systems, and business operations. The Scopus search queries were applied within the article title, abstract, and keywords fields, while the IEEE Xplore search queries were applied within all metadata fields. These search queries are presented in Table 2.

To enhance our search queries, several restrictions are being applied, which are summarized in Table 1. Both searches have the same restrictions, which are limited to journal and conference papers, open access only, publications written in English, and papers published between 2020 and 2025. These restrictions ensured that the retrieved studies are relevant to the current day and align with the objectives of the review.

Table 1 Search Restrictions

Databases	Restrictions
SCOPUS	- Year: 2020 – 2025 - Document type: Article & Conference paper - Publication stage: Final - Source type: Journal & Conference proceedings - Language: English - Open access: all open access
IEEE	- Journals - Conferences - Year: 2020 – 2025 - Open access only

Table 2 Search Queries

Database	Sentences
SCOPUS	(TITLE-ABS-KEY ("artificial intelligence" OR "AI") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ("decision support system*" OR "decision making" OR "decision support") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ("operations management" OR "business operations" OR "production" OR "supply chain" OR "logistics" OR "service operations")) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (business OR firm* OR enterprise* OR organization* OR company OR companies OR industry) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (performance OR efficiency OR "operational performance" OR productivity))
IEEE	("artificial intelligence" OR "AI" OR "machine learning") AND ("decision support" OR "decision support system" OR "decision making" OR "decision aid") AND ("operations management" OR "business operations" OR "operations" OR "production" OR "supply chain" OR "logistics" OR "service operations") AND (performance OR efficiency OR "operational performance" OR productivity)

B. Eligibility Criteria

To ensure the selected studies align with the objectives of this systematic literature review, explicit inclusion and exclusion criteria are being applied to the screening process. These criteria were there to filter studies that examine AI-enabled decision support in business operations and exclude studies that examine AI-enabled automated decision making, studies that are purely technical, and those with no business or service operations context.

The selected studies have to meet all of the following inclusion and exclusion criteria. First, the study must involve operational activities in business or service operations, this doesn't limited to manufacturing, supply chain, logistics, production, or other organizational operational activities. Second, the study must involve AI-enabled decision support used by human decision makers. AI-enabled decision support is defined as providing recommendations, predictions, or insights or to be precise, AI-enabled decision support to provide human oversight. Third, the study must be in the English language because English is the common language used in research papers. Fourth, Studies must measured effect of decision support and operational performance to answer research objectives. Fifth, the study must be written between 2020 and 2025 because that is when AI starts to evolve rapidly.

The studies that are excluded primarily focused on AI-enabled automated decision making, and no business or service operations activities. AI-enabled automated decision-making fully automates their decision-making, which means that human decision-makers are not involved in the process. Studies that were conducted with no business or service operations activities, such as educational, military, and government, are excluded from the studies. Studies that are not in the English language are excluded. The same applies to outside 2020 and 2025. Lastly, the papers that can't be downloaded are excluded as well. Table 3 presents the inclusion and exclusion criteria applied to the title and abstract screening process and full text review of the retrieved studies.

Table 3 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
IC1: Operational activities in business or service operations	EC1: No business or service operations activities
IC2: AI-Enabled decision support used by human decision makers	EC2: AI automation decision making
IC3: English language	EC3: Not in English
IC4: Measured effect of AI decision support on human decision making & Operational Performance	EC4: Paper is not available for download

IC5: Studies written between 2020 and 2025
 EC5: Published before 2020 or after 2025

C. Selection Process

This study selection process followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) guidelines to ensure transparency in the reporting process. This selection process is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1 PRISMA Flow Diagram

In the identification stage, a total of 759 studies were retrieved from SCOPUS and IEEE Xplore databases, which include 433 studies from SCOPUS and 326 studies from IEEE Xplore. All the 759 studies were consolidated and managed using the Covidence systematic review software, and an automated duplicate check by Covidence was performed, resulting in 0 duplicate records. But one duplicate record was identified and removed manually, which resulted in 758 studies for the title and abstract screening process.

The remaining 758 studies were screened based on the title and abstract to assess whether the studies are AI-enabled decision support used by human decision makers and Operational activities in business or service operations. Studies that were not in the IC1 and IC2 will be

excluded during the screening process. The following screening results in 656 excluded studies, and 102 studies retain further evaluation.

Full text review was performed for all 102 studies and was examined carefully to verify whether it meets the eligibility criteria and aligns with the study's objectives. As a result, 87 studies were excluded, the majority of them came from the wrong intervention (72 studies), as most of the studies focus on automated AI-decision making. 8 studies were excluded as they don't measure the effect of AI decision support and operational performance. Lastly, 4 and 3 studies were excluded because paper is not available for download and are not involved in business or service operations activities.

After completion of full text review, only 15 studies met all the inclusion and exclusion criteria, which will then be synthesized in the results and discussion section.

D. Data Extraction

Data are collected through a data extraction form to collect information about the selected studies. The extracted information from the selected studies includes:

- Bibliographic details (publication title, database source, publication venue, publication year)
- Author information (author name, author country)
- Research characteristics (research type, research method, research subject)
- Contextual information (operational context, geographic distribution context)
- Findings (AI decision-making task, effects of AI-enabled decision support on human decision making, operational performance)

E. Data Analysis

The studies used a combination of graphical, tabular data, and narrative methods to identify recurring patterns, themes, and answer the research questions. This is shown in descriptive findings and analytical findings in result section. The descriptive findings were

conducted to summarize characteristic of selected studies. The data used in descriptive findings include research method, author country, decision-making task, operational context, and publication year. Analytical findings were conducted to analyze how AI-enabled decision support influences human operational decision-making and improves operational performance in business operations.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following results and discussion are structured into three sections: (A) Descriptive Findings, (B) Analytical Findings, and (C) Discussion.

A. Descriptive Findings

The systematic review identified 15 selected studies, which were categorized by publication year, research method, author country, decision-making task, and operational context.

Figure 2 Publication Year

2020 and 2022 are excluded from Figure 2, as there are no selected studies to improve clarity and readability. Figure 2 shows the publication year distribution of the 15 selected studies from Scopus and IEEE Xplore. The results show that 15 selected studies appear to concentrate on later period of the studies timeframe (2025), while there are fewer publication studies in the earlier year.

Table 4 Research Method Distribution

Research Method	Studies
Case Study	8
Experimental Study	5
Mixed Study	2

Figure 3 Research Method Percentage

Table 4 shows the distribution of research methods of the 15 selected studies. Research methods are categorized to describe the research design of the selected studies. The result shows that there are only 3 research methods among 15 selected studies, which are case study, experimental studies, and mixed method study. Case studies are determined when the study examines an AI-enabled decision support system used in real life or applied operational context, this include studies that use operational data such as manufacturing data from tire manufacturing processes, real shoe manufacturing, and sportswear manufacturing. On the other hand, experimental studies are determined when the study examined controlled testing of a prototype, simulation, or trained model with the established procedures, this may include studies that simulate a synthetic shop floor to check whether an AI-enabled decision support system works correctly in the system. Lastly, we determine a mixed methods study when the study combines two methods, which are qualitative and quantitative. For example, one study combined two research methods, which are case study and questionnaire survey, to build decision support indicators using AHP. As for data collection techniques, such as questionnaires, interviews, observations, and simulations are part of the study procedures, which mean we treated as supporting methods unless it formed a distinct analytical component within the research design. Overall, case studies dominate the research method among the selected studies, while mixed method studies have the least selected studies. Figure 3 illustrates the percentages of the distribution of research methods of the 15 selected studies, offering a visual representation of the proportions of the research methods.

Table 5 Author Affiliations by Country Distribution

Country	Count
Germany	13
China	10
Portugal	7
Hungary	7
Mexico	5
USA	4
Estonia	4
Canada	3
Hong Kong	3
Norway	3
Denmark	3
United Kingdom	2
South Korea	1
Saudi Arabia	1
France	1
Total	67

Note: Authors with multiple country affiliations (Germany and Hong Kong) were counted under each associated country. The total count of unique authors is 65.

Figure 4 Author Affiliations by Region

Table 5 shows the distributions of author affiliations by country, while Figure 4 shows Author affiliations by region. In the European countries, most of the contributions are driven by countries such as Germany (13), Portugal (7), and Hungary (7). In the Asian countries, China dominates the author affiliations (10), followed by small contributions from Hong Kong (3), South Korea (1), and Saudi Arabia (1). On the other hand, North America is almost distributed equally across 3 countries, which are Mexico (5), the United States (4), and Canada (3). Overall, the studies reflect a strong concentration on European institutions, mainly in Germany.

Table 6 Decision-Making Task Distribution

Decision-Making Task	Studies
Planning & Scheduling	7
Monitoring & Diagnosis	3
Supplier Decisions	3

Quality Control	1
Human Resource Decisions	1

Figure 5 Decision-Making Task

Table 6 shows the distributions of decision-making tasks of the 15 selected studies, while Figure 5 shows the visual representation of the proportions of decision-making tasks. The results show that there are 5 task categories which are planning & scheduling, monitoring & Diagnosis, supplier decisions, quality control, and human resources decisions. Planning & scheduling discuss about scheduling related decisions and coordination decisions, which include some task such as irrigation scheduling, production scheduling, and distribution and logistics planning. Monitoring & diagnosis discuss about identifying operational conditions and support anomaly detection, this include tasks such as, process monitoring and data exploration and anomaly detection. Supplier decisions talks about supplier assessment based on the criteria, this include tasks such as supplier/vendor selection and ranking and supplier risk evaluation. Lastly, quality control discuss about process compliance, while human resources decisions covers workforce selection decisions, such as personal selection and hiring decisions. Overall, planning & scheduling are the most researched, while quality control and human resource decisions have the least research focus.

Table 7 Operational Context Distribution

Operational Context	Studies
SCM & Logistics	4
Manufacturing	4
Sector Specific Operations	3
Digital Business	2
HR & Projects Operations	2

Figure 6 Operational Context

Table 7 and Figure 6 show the distribution of the 15 selected studies combined with a visual representation of the proportions of the operational context. The result shows that manufacturing and supply chain management have the most examined context. Manufacturing discuss about production environment, which include tire manufacturing processes, shoe manufacturing, and sportswear manufacturing, while supply chain management and logistics include automotive supply chain and logistics/ warehouse projects. On the other hand, digital business talks about business operations digitally, such as e-commerce operations and cloud based ERP environment. Human resources & project operations discuss people and project which include agile software project management. Lastly, Sector specific operations combines agriculture operations, healthcare service operations, and offshore operations. Overall, in operational context SCM & logistics and manufacturing have the most represented in operational context, while digital business and HR & project operations are less focus context.

B. Analytical Findings

After explaining the descriptive findings in the previous section, this section provides an analytical synthesis of the 15 selected studies to address the research question of this study.

Table 8 synthesizes 9 out of 15 selected studies on the influences of AI-enabled decision support on human operational decision-making. Across the studies, recurring influences were identified and categorized into decision-making efficiency, adaptive decision-making, situational awareness, decision explainability, and decision-making confidence.

Three studies reported that there is an improvement in decision-making efficiency, which is primarily achieved through reduced information overload for managers, planners, schedulers, and operators [16], improved project visibility enabled by live AI-based decision support [17], and more timely interventions resulting in faster decision responses for resource capacity planning and scheduling tasks [18].

AI-enabled decision support also influences adaptive decision-making through supporting non-expert decision makers in interpreting the operational information and providing guidance in decision-making under dynamic and unplanned conditions [19].

Three studies identified that the influence on improvement in situational awareness comes from gaining insights during operational process deviations [19], increased production transparency to identify operational states and process anomalies [20], and gaining insight through a list of abnormal events [21].

Other studies indicate that AI-enabled decision support improves decision explainability, manifested through the reduction of supplier selection criteria and the number of suppliers, which therefore supports supplier selection decisions [22] and provide supports for the supplier escalation decisions [23]. Finally, one study reported that there is an increase in decision-making confidence, which is reflected through feedback mechanisms that support the reflective decision-making process of personal selection tasks [24].

Table 8 AI-Enabled Decision Support Influences Human Operational Decision-Making

Type of Influence	Description	Source
Decision-making efficiency	Reduced information overload	[16],
	Improved project visibility	[17],
	Timely interventions and faster decision responses	[18]
Adaptive decision-making	Support for non-expert decision makers	[19]
	Supports decisions in dynamic and unplanned conditions	

Situational awareness	Improved insights during operational deviations	[19], [20], [21]
	Increased production transparency	
	Insight into abnormal operational conditions	
Decision explainability	Interpretable supplier selection decisions	[22], [23]
	Explainable supplier escalations decisions	
Decision-making confidence	Feedback supporting reflective decision-making	[24]

Table 9 synthesizes 9 out of 15 selected studies on the operational performance impact of AI-enabled decision support in business operations. Most of the studies indicate a multiple impact on different kinds of operational performance. The study's impact was identified and categorized into improves productivity, improves resources efficiency, improves resources management, improves process efficiency, increases operational resilience, and improve risk management.

Two studies reported an improvement in operational performance through productivity, reflected by an increase in crop production [25] and increased inventory turnover achieved by demand forecasting and demand management [26]. Operational performance impact also includes improvement in resource efficiency, which primarily discuss on reductions in resource consumption and costs such as reduced water consumption [25] and reduced operating costs [26]. In addition, three studies identified that the operational performance impact of AI-enabled decision support in business operations improves resource management, which includes improved workload optimization by better distributing imbalanced workload tasks, improved resource planning by adapting the allocation of human resources [17], and improved resource capacity through more effective planning and scheduling tasks [18].

The most frequently reported operational performance impact of the studies is improved process efficiency, with 6 studies. The 6 studies reported a reduction in order processing time by accelerating orders through decision support [26], reduced late deliveries by improved scheduling decisions under uncertainty [27],

and eliminated unplanned downtime by preventing unexpected production micro-stoppages, which cause an improvement in the machine availability [28]. After that, there is also an improvement in inventory management through price adjustment predictions [29], improved supply chain efficiency through effective supplier selection decisions [30], improved sprint performance and backlog management through enhanced visibility of sprint progress and effective backlog prioritization. Lastly, reduced defect resolution time, which indicates faster identification and resolution of the defect [17].

Only one studies discuss the increase of operational resilience through adaptation in supplier escalation decisions. There is also a reported impact on minimizing operational risks through proactive identification and mitigation of supplier disruptions [23], increased supplier safety and security by AI-assisted supplier selection and evaluation criteria [30], and improved risk response plans by identifying and mitigating the project risks [17]. Finally, the operational performance impact on operational sustainability through the supplier selection process that secure long term relationships with suppliers [30].

Table 9 Operational Performance Impacts of AI-Enabled Decision Support in Business Operations

Performance Impact	Description	Source
Improves productivity	Increased crop production	[25],
	Increased inventory turnover	[26]
Improves resources efficiency	Reduced water consumption	[25],
	Reduced operating costs	[26]
Improves resources management	Improved workload optimization	
	Improved project resource planning	[17], [18]
	Improved resource capacity planning	
Improves process efficiency	Reduced order processing time	[17], [26],
	Reduced late deliveries	[27], [28],
	Eliminated unplanned downtime	[29], [30]

	Enhanced machine availability	
	Improved inventory management	
	Improved supply chain efficiency	
	Improved sprint performance tracking	
	Improved backlog management	
	Reduced defect resolution time	
Increases operational resilience	Enhanced supply chain resilience	[23]
	Minimized operational risks	
Improves risk management	Increased supplier safety and security	[17], [23], [30]
	Improved risk response plans	
Improves operational sustainability	Improved supply chain sustainability	[30]

C. Discussion

This systematic literature review synthesizes 15 selected studies, which are then divided into 2 sections: descriptive and analytical findings. The descriptive results indicate that the research on AI-enabled decision support on humans decision making in business operations has grown fast in recent years, which can be seen by the amount of activity in publications in 2025, with a noticeable jump in interest in the topic. Based on the studies in Scopus and IEEE suggest that AI-enabled decision support involves topics about business, management, technical, and engineering-oriented research.

The research method of the studies indicates that most studies in this field use a case study approach, this indicate that most researchers focus on how AI-enabled decision support works and how it can be applied into real world operational scenarios. On the other hand, experimental studies contribute evidence in different kinds of ways. Some use controlled lab settings, which are suited to measuring influence on decision-making outcomes. Other experimental studies use simulations to validate their models using predefined scenarios to measure quantitative performance. Lastly, although mixed method studies provide the least amount of selected studies, they provide

qualitative and quantitative measures which well suited to examine both decision outcomes and operational performance.

Author affiliations by country in this field are concentrated mainly in Europe, followed by contributions from Asia and North America. This pattern may be related to how some European countries have stronger industrial adoption of digital technologies, particularly in manufacturing industries. However, with the limited number of selected studies we got and only coming from a few regions, these findings may not apply to other countries.

For the decision-making tasks, the studies are mostly about planning and scheduling. This can refer to how AI decision support is mostly used in uncertainty and time-pressure situations. This helps respond quickly to the changing situation. Lastly, there is an operational context which is mostly concentrated on Supply chain & logistics and manufacturing. These 2 context dominate the context of the studies, which indicates that most of the studies focus on environments that need to process a lot of data, as it can be noticeably different and easier to observe in terms of improvement.

The analytical synthesis provides 2 insights from the 15 selected papers, which are AI-enabled decision support influences human operational decision-making and operational performance impacts of AI-enabled decision support in Business Operations. The type of influence on human operational decision-making mostly comes from decision-making efficiency and situational awareness. Decision-making efficiency is achieved through reducing information overload, improving project visibility, and supporting timely interventions and faster decision responses. This influence helps decision makers process a lot of information at once and respond more quickly to certain conditions.

On the other hand, situational awareness is achieved through improved insights into operational deviations, abnormal conditions, and production transparency. This helps decision makers to better understand the situation or what happens in the system, as it allows them to detect problems earlier and

maintain control of the problems. Beyond the efficiency and awareness, the studies also identify adaptive decision-making, decision explainability, and decision-making confidence. Adaptive decision-making provides guidance to adapt faster without prior experience. While decision explainability helps provide explanations for its answer to decision makers. It can help decision maker understand the reasoning behind the insight. Similarly, decision-making confidence helps provide feedback reflecting on past decisions. Overall, it helps provide insight, clarity, transparency, and confidence in decision-making.

Based on the studies, process efficiency has the most reported impact on operational performance. Process efficiency reported such improvement in reduced order processing time, reduced late deliveries, eliminated unplanned downtime, enhanced machine availability, improved inventory management, improved efficiency in supply chain, and better agile execution, which includes improved sprint performance tracking, backlog management, and backlog management. All these studies indicate that AI-enabled decision support mostly delivers value by improving process efficiency in business operations. In addition, resource related appears in 2 distinct forms, which are resource efficiency and resource management. This means that AI-enabled decision support not only optimizes resource use but also improves its managerial process through improved workload, improved resource planning in the project, and capacity.

Improvement in productivity, risk management, resilience, and sustainability appears less studies than process efficiency. Improvement in productivity is reflected through higher crop production and increased inventory turnover, which indicates that AI-enabled decision-making creates greater operational output. On the other hand, improved risk management can be done through minimized operational risks, enhanced supplier safety and security, and improved risk response, which in term mean helps strengthen the operational robustness. Improves resilience and sustainability in operational reflect the ability to manage disruptions and sustain long term operational relationship such as reliable supplier

relationships. Overall, the impact in operational performance discuss about improvement primarily in process efficiency, productivity, risk management, and resource-related efficiency, while other impacts are less discussed in the study.

IV. CONCLUSION

This systematic literature review synthesized and examined how AI-enabled decision support influence human operational decision-making and improves operational performance in business operations. The studies synthesized findings from 15 selected studies, which provide insights for businesses seeking to implement AI decision support systems. Based on the objectives of our research, the findings shows that AI-enabled decision support mainly influences decision-making efficiency, adaptability, situational awareness, explainability, and confidence, while operational performance improvement comes from process efficiency, productivity, risk management, resource-related efficiency, resilience, and sustainability. Most of the studies focus on improvement in process efficiency, while resilience and sustainability are less discussed in the studies. This suggests there is still room for research in the resilience and sustainability topic on AI-enabled decision support. Overall, this studies conclude that AI-enabled decision support in business operations is largely efficiency driven and process focused.

There are several limitations in this study. First, the number of selected studies is relatively small. Second, the reviewed study covers diverse business operations and decision-making tasks, which result in heterogeneous evaluations on reported effects and operational performance impacts. Third, all selected studies are based on the positive aspects of AI decision support on humans.

Future research should expand empirical investigations across different databases, as this research was only conducted on Scopus and IEEE Xplore. In addition, future studies should evaluate within single operational domains or service operations to enable stronger empirical

conclusions. Finally, future research should examine the negative aspects of AI-decision support on humans, as this study primary focus on the positive impact.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The dataset used in this studies is accessible at the following link:

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION

Ricky Oesmandy: Conceptualization, Literature Search, Screening, Data Extraction, Visualization, Analysis, Manuscript Preparation. Desi Maya Kristin: Supervision, Investigation, Project Administration, Validation. Mulyono: Co-Supervisor, Project Administration, Investigation, Validation.

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